

The Action of Organic Compounds on Sodium Hydrogen Sulphate

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The treatment of trisodium hydrogen disulphate or sodium sesquisulphate, $\text{Na}_3\text{H}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ with successive quantities of 99.95 per cent. ethyl alcohol has been shown to cause a small but progressive fall in acidity in the solid residues. After leaving the salt in contact with separate quantities of alcohol for six consecutive days the acidity fell from 18.64 to 17.75 per cent. H_2SO_4 (total fall = 0.89 per cent.). The efforts of Butler and Dunncliff (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 649) to make a continuous extraction were unsuccessful. This continuous extraction has now been carried out under reduced pressure in a Soxhlet and bumping entirely prevented by bubbling through the alcohol in the flask, a slow stream of specially dried air by means of a capillary tube. The pressure was so adjusted that the alcohol boiled at 45°C. Extractions were carried out from 8-10 hours daily and the salt was allowed to remain under alcohol overnight.

Acidity on successive days in ether dried samples: 18.66; 18.64; 18.61; 18.59; 18.56; 18.51; 18.50; 18.47; 18.48% H_2SO_4 (total fall after nine days, 0.18% H_2SO_4).

Crystalline $\text{Na}_3\text{H}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, obtained by the fractional crystallisation of a solution of sodium hydrogen sulphate in water, is also unattacked by alcohol or ether and it has been shown (*loc. cit.*) that the sesquisulphate is a definite compound and not a mixture of the normal and hydrogen sulphate.

The corresponding hydrogen sulphate of ammonium, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{H}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ behaves in a similar manner (Dunncliff, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 476).

The sulphuric acid extractable by alcohol is shown in dotted area. An asymmetric formula is proposed because the extraction of the solid salt appears to take place without solution. The formula of the sesqui salt would then become

not $\text{R}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{RHSO}_4$, a formula which would imply that the RHSO_4 part of the molecule could be attacked by alcohol to which $\text{R}_3\text{H}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ is inert. The formation of the sesquisulphate from a symmetrical formula would necessitate either solution or intramolecular change and neither of these suggestions appears to be feasible.

Class (c).—The ordinary formula is suggested

(Lowry, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 1923, pp. 160 and 353).

Hence, the stability of the hydrogen sulphates to alcohol and ether increases progressively with increase in the atomic weight of the alkali metal in the salt. It is interesting to note that compounds of classes (a) and (b) are deliquescent at ordinary humidities while those of class (c) and the sesquisulphates of sodium and ammonium are not. Since sulphuric acid is hygroscopic it suggests that this property in acid sulphates may be associated with a sulphur atom combined with two hydroxy groups as shown in the formulae proposed. A remarkable feature of these results is the sudden manner in which this property changes.

The amorphous form of sodium sesquisulphate obtained by the action of alcohol on sodium hydrogen sulphate has chemical properties identical with those exhibited by the crystalline variety of the same

compound obtained by the fractional crystallisation of an aqueous solution of sodium hydrogen sulphate.

It is contended that sodium hydrogen sulphate cannot be described as "soluble" in alcohol since it has not been found possible to obtain any alcoholic extract of sodium hydrogen sulphate in which sodium sulphate and sulphuric acid are present in stoichiometric proportions. Alcohol does not dissolve sodium hydrogen sulphate—it decomposes it.

Hydrogen sulphates of sodium formed from sodium sulphate and sulphuric acid, and containing more than 40.83 per cent. of sulphuric acid, are acted on by ether yielding the hydrogen sulphate having the empirical formula, NaHSO_4 .

A systematic examination of the system Na_2SO_4 - H_2SO_4 - $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$ has recently been carried out by Dunicliff and his co-workers. The equilibrium has been studied (a) by the action of alcohol on sodium hydrogen sulphate and (b) by the action of alcoholic sulphuric acids on sodium hydrogen sulphate and, while experiments on the limited range attackable by method (a) have presented no great difficulty, those carried out by method (b) have been complicated by the peptisation of the solid phase and sometimes the entire contents of the tube solidified into a firm jelly. By a physico-chemical method it has been shown that the solid phases in contact with alcoholic sulphuric acids having concentrations between 20 and 40 per cent. H_2SO_4 have an acidity of about 41%, corresponding with sodium hydrogen sulphate, NaHSO_4 .

In view of the statement that ordinary sodium hydrogen sulphate is stable to continuous extraction with ether, the results in Tables V and VI (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 658, 659) obtained by the extraction of the "mush" with ether show that the extractability of sulphuric acid from sodium hydrogen sulphate by ether

depends upon the physical state of the substance. Thus, in the gelatinous state, in which a large surface is exposed to the liquid, ether slowly extracts sulphuric acid while in the powdered state the amount of sulphuric acid removed is negligible over the same interval of time (maximum time investigated = 3 weeks' extraction in each case).

It has been found that many other organic compounds extract sulphuric acid from sodium hydrogen sulphate. Experiment with methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *iso*-propyl, butyl, primary *iso*-butyl and *iso*-amyl alcohols show that the weight of alcohol required to reduce the acidity of a given weight of sodium hydrogen sulphate to about 18.70 per cent. increases with the weight of the alkyl group in combination with the hydroxyl.

Table I shows this relationship and it is remarkable that up to the butyl alcohols the molecular proportions of alcohol to hydrogen sulphate are about the same throughout.

TABLE I.

Action of Aliphatic Saturated Alcohols on Sodium Hydrogen Sulphate.

Alcohol.	B. p. at 730 mm. (Labore).	Wt. of alcohol Wt. of NaHSO ₄ .	Approx. molec. proportions of C ₂ H ₆ O to NaHSO ₄ .	Acidity of residue after ether extraction.
CH ₃ OH ...	63.5	3.5	13.1:1	18.72
C ₂ H ₅ OH ...	78.1	5.5	14.4:1	18.69
C ₃ H ₇ OH(<i>n</i>) ...	95.5	7.4	14.8:1	18.68
C ₃ H ₇ OH(<i>iso</i>) ...	80.5	7.6	15.2:1	18.67
C ₄ H ₉ OH(<i>n</i>) ...	116.0	9.0	14.6:1	18.79
C ₄ H ₉ OH(<i>iso</i> -primary).	109.0	9.1	14.6:1	18.69
C ₄ H ₉ OH(<i>iso</i> -butyl carbinol).	129.5	26.1	35.4:1	18.68

Benzyl alcohol alone extracts acid from the salt but equal parts of benzyl alcohol and ether cause a very small fall in acidity.

Ethyl aceto-acetate extracts acid slowly.

Borneol dissolved in ether extracted some acid from the salt.

The hydroxy compounds, phenol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, dissolved in ether, were without action on sodium hydrogen sulphate.

Action of Ketones.

Acetone, b. p. 55·8°C.

Acetone: NaHSO_4 :: 7 : 1. Residual acidity of solid 27·44—27·48%. The residue was treated with more acetone; residual acidity 18·62%. Acetone: NaHSO_4 :: 10 : 1 Residual acidity of solid, 18·61—18·68%. The liquid phase changed colour on standing and, after three weeks, was dark brown and viscous owing to secondary changes between the extracted sulphuric acid and the acetone.

Methyl ethyl ketone, b. p. 79·5°C.

Ketone: NaHSO_4 :: 7 : 1; time of interaction 20 hours.

Acidity of residue, 35·31 per cent.

Ketone: residue :: 5 : 1; further treatment overnight.

Acidity of residue, 20·36 per cent.

Two further extractions gave 19·90 and 18·64 per cent. respectively.

Acetophenone, b. p. 199—200°C.

Ketone: NaHSO_4 :: 11 : 1 (interaction 24 hours).

Acidity of residue, 35·33 per cent.

Benzophenone, m. p. 47·6°C.

Ketone: NaHSO_4 :: 7·3 parts to 10 parts : 1.

The ketone was dissolved in a weight of ether about 14 to 15 times the weight of sodium hydrogen sulphate taken. Fall in acidity negligible.

Similar experiments performed on benzoquinone and camphor dissolved in excess of ether gave a negligible fall in acidity.

Pyridine and quinoline combine with the hydrogen sulphate to form gelatinous substances.

It is observed that, for an extraction by ketones, $\text{CH}_3\text{CO.X}$ to a corresponding degree, the greater the group X, the larger the ratio $\frac{\text{weight of ketone}}{\text{weight of hydrogen sulphate}}$ becomes.

Hence though, for a given alcohol or ketone, the amount of decomposition is dependent on the variations the above ratio, it is clear that for different alcohols and ketones, the solid phase developed in contact with a given organic liquid is dependent on some factor other than the concentration of the acid in the organic liquid.

From the above results it appears that compounds which contain a primary or secondary alcoholic group or ketones in which there is one methyl group interact with sodium hydrogen sulphate and extract sulphuric acid.

An interesting point arises. Since alcohol reacts with sodium hydrogen sulphate, can it act catalytically? Thus: a small quantity of alcohol is dissolved in a considerable quantity of ether. Sodium hydrogen sulphate is treated with such a quantity of the mixture that if $\frac{2}{3}$ of the sulphuric acid were extracted from the hydrogen sulphate presented to it, the solution would still have a concentration of sulphuric acid within the limits of the concentration of sulphuric acid in alcohol which are in equilibrium with the intermediate sulphate $\text{Na}_2\text{H}(\text{SO}_4)_2$. This would suggest that the sulphuric acid is extracted by the alcohol which then hands it over to the ether, this process being continued until the concentration of the sulphuric acid in the mixed solvents passes beyond the limits of the existence of the intermediate

sulphate. (This was not possible owing to the amount of alcohol-ether mixture used.) Experiments give no support to this theory in the case of either alcohol or acetone. The amount of acid extracted decreases as the concentration of alcohol or acetone diminishes. This decrease in extraction was also observed in the case of benzyl alcohol.

TABLE II.

Action of Mixtures of Ethyl Alcohol and Ether on Sodium Hydrogen Sulphate.

$\frac{\text{Wt. of alcohol.}}{\text{Wt. of ether.}}$	Wt. of mixture used per g. of sodium hydrogen sulphate.	Acid extractable 0.272 g. Acid actually extracted.	Acidity of solid residue % H_2SO_4 .
1 : 4.57	4.78	0.1787	27.90
1 : 9.10	6.94	0.1729	28.43
1 : 18.2	7.60	0.0972	34.42
1 : 36.4	6.77	0.0823	35.50

TABLE III.

Action of Mixtures of Acetone and Ether on Sodium Hydrogen Sulphate.

$\frac{\text{Wt. of acetone.}}{\text{Wt. of ether.}}$	Wt. of mixture used per g. of sodium hydrogen sulphate.	Acid extractable 0.272 g. Acid actually extracted.	Acidity of solid residue % H_2SO_4 .
1:1	10	0.0850	35.90
1.2:1	11	0.0966	34.47
1.4:1	12	0.1739	28.34
1.6:1	13	0.1740	28.33
1.8:1	14	0.1760	28.16
2.0:1	15	0.1754	28.28

The last three results are roughly of the order of the residual acidity when 7 parts of pure acetone react with 1 of NaHSO_4 .

The frequency with which solids having acidities of about 35 and 28 per cent. acidity are developed is remarkable.

It is suggested that the reaction is due to the ionisation of the alcohol or the 'enol' form developed or present in such ketones as react and which are limited to these containing the CH_3CO group. The action of the ether appears to decrease the ionisation of alcohols and the "enolisation" of ketones since the specific conductivities of alcohol and acetone are progressively decreased by increasing quantities of ether. The determinations given in Tables IV and VI were made on the material actually used in the experiments on sodium hydrogen sulphate.

It will be observed that, though the specific conductivity of acetone is greater than that of alcohol, its ability to extract sulphuric acid from sodium hydrogen sulphate is much smaller.

Specific Conductivities of Mixtures of two Organic Liquids.

TABLE IV.

Alcohol and Acetone.

Percentage of acetone in the mixture.	Specific conductivities.
0	2.29×10^{-6} mhos
20	3.06×10^{-6} „
40	3.73×10^{-6} „
60	4.35×10^{-6} „
80	5.04×10^{-6} „
100	5.28×10^{-6} „

TABLE V.
Alcohol and Ether.

Percentage of alcohol in the mixture.	Specific conductivities.
100	22.9×10^{-7} mhos
80	14.3×10^{-7} „
60	12.3×10^{-7} „
40	6.6×10^{-7} „
20	0.86×10^{-7} „
0	0.19×10^{-7} „

TABLE VI.
Acetone and Ether.

Percentage of acetone in the mixture.	Specific conductivities.
100	52.8×10^{-7} mhos
80	31.8×10^{-7} „
60	15.6×10^{-7} „
40	3.8×10^{-7} „
20	0.34×10^{-7} „
0	0.19×10^{-7} „

So far, the attempts to find an adequate chemical interpretation (intermediate compound formation) or physico-chemical explanation of these results have been unsuccessful.

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